

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ

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**ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ
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1-СОҢ**

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CULTURAL ASPECTS OF PARALINGUSITIC DEVICES

Иқтибос келтириш учун: КНАКИМОВ М.Кх., MELIKUZIEV А.Л. Cultural aspects of paralingusitic devises // Тадқиқот ва инновациялар. № 1 (2023) Б. 31-34.

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ANNOTATSIYA

Muloqot jarayoni murakkab struktura hisoblanadi. Soʻzlashuvchilar bu jarayonda verbal va noverbal vositalardan foydalanadilar. Har bir jamiyat bu ifoda vositalaridan foydalanar ekan, ularda lingvokulturologik xususiyatlar aks etadi. Mazkur maqolada noverbal vositalarning paralingvokulturologik jihatlari tahlil ostiga olingan. Bunda turli xalqlarning muloqot jarayonida qoʻllaniladigan paralingvistik birliklari oʻzaro qiyoslab oʻrganilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: lingvokulturologiya, paralingvistika, noverbal vositalar, lingvomadaniy paradigma, madaniy universalিয়া, intonatsion modulyatsiyasi, nutq tempi, tovush boʻyogʻi.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Коммуникативный процесс представляет собой сложную структуру. Говорящие используют в этом процессе вербальные и невербальные средства. Поскольку каждое общество использует эти средства выражения, они отражают языковые и культурные особенности. В данной статье анализируются паралингуокультурные аспекты невербальных средств. В сравнении исследуются паралингвистические единицы, используемые в процессе общения разных народов.

Ключевые слова: лингвокультурология, паралингвистика, невербальные средства, лингвокультурная парадигма, культурная универсальность, интонационная модуляция, темп речи, звуковая окраска.

ANNOTATION

The communication process is a complex structure. Speakers use both verbal and nonverbal means in this process. As each society uses these means of expression, they reflect lingvoculturological features. This article analyzes the paralinguoculturological aspects of nonverbal means. In this case, the paralinguistic units used in the communication process of different peoples are studied by comparative study.

Keywords: lingvoculturology, paralinguistics, noverbal means, lingvocultural paradigm, cultural universality, intonation modulation, speech tempo, sound color.

Today, one of the newly formed directions of modern linguistics, in particular extralinguistics, is the science of linguo-cultural studies or linguo-cultural studies. A relatively perfect study of this field remains one of the priority tasks of linguists at the moment. Linguistics emerged as an independent branch of linguistics in the 90s of the 20th century. This term was coined by V.N., the then head of the Moscow Phraseological School. Prominent representatives of Telia and Maktav V. Shaklein, V.A. Maslova, Y.S. Stepanov, V.V. Vorobev, [1.P.175].

According to the opinion of linguists, linguoculturology focuses on the relationship between man and culture. In particular, linguoculturology as a special field of science has given birth to several concepts in linguistics, such as linguocultural paradigm, linguoculture, cultural scene, cultural language, cultural text, subculture, cultural universality, cultural authority, cultural traditions, cultural process, cultural space, cultural beauty [2.P.91].

Specific features of cultural relations between peoples are considered as a success of mutual cultural adaptation. Its important role has been noted by many researchers in this field. Cross-cultural interactions in nonverbal behavior have been extensively studied by scholars in social psychology.

Many researchers have analyzed examples from the communication of representatives of different ethnic groups in various aspects of non-verbal communication. The world-famous film actor Ch. Chaplin said: "Show me how you move and gesture, and I will immediately tell you where you were born." It should be noted that in many cases, non-verbal means of communication (gestures, facial expressions, units related to the quality of the voice) are used in order to overcome communication barriers in the process of not understanding or not knowing the language of a representative of another nationality.

Also, cross-cultural differences in non-verbal communication, which create communication barriers, often lead to misunderstandings. As can be seen from the above points, the linguistic and cultural research of non-verbal means is one of the most important issues of modern linguistics.

Human speech is a unique complex phenomenon, and since it is impossible to clearly indicate the units related to it in writing, the need for thorough research of speech arises. In the past century, microlinguistics, which has become traditional linguistic research in linguistics, that is, the internal side of speech (segmentable units) phoneme, morpheme, word, phrase, sentence and its internal structures, has been studied. At the moment, its external plan, including various intonation modulations of the voice, speech tempo, sound color, various gestures, facial expressions, mannerisms of the interlocutor are attracting linguists. In the process of conveying information to the listener, he needs auxiliary (non-verbal) tools that are close to language. Paralinguistic tools are a secondary tool that naturally follows and complements the speech in the communication of every person's society [4.P.50].

Non-linguistic tools perform the task of bringing the speech to a certain standard depending on the situation, in particular, of condensing it, clearly expressing the addressee's goal. It should be noted here that non-verbal means of verbal communication are universal regardless of where and with whom we communicate. But the culture of each country develops according to its own laws, and each country has its own characteristics of non-verbal communication. The conversation process is not limited to the content of the speech. In some cases, most of the information is given by linguistic and non-linguistic means, as well as by means of national-cultural communication, specific to the national etiquette of the participants in the conversation.

Every nation begins human interaction, treatment and communication with a greeting. They have special greeting customs. In the process of greeting, the following paralinguistic situations are observed: shaking hands (mainly in men), face-to-face (mainly in women), patting on the shoulder, shaking hands, kissing. For example, Burmese, Mongolian and Laplanders can sniff each other as a greeting, and Eskimos can punch a stranger on the shoulder. The people of Amazonia express their greetings by clapping each other's shoulders, and the people of Polynesia express their greetings by hugging and patting the interlocutor's shoulder [5.P.42]. The greeting custom of the Uzbek, Japanese and Korean peoples is expressed through various non-verbal means according to age, circumstances, position, gender and rituals. In particular, Uzbeks say "assalamu alaykum", "vaalaikum assalam" with two hands, put their hand on their chest, hug, rub their hands and shoulders, kiss their foreheads, lift each other up when they have not seen each other for a long time, women shake their shoulders, kiss and wave their hands. Japanese people bow when they greet each other. In Turkic peoples, shaking hands during a conversation is an integral part of etiquette, and this state means that a certain person has a good attitude towards the interlocutor. Handshakes vary from nation to nation and culture.

There is also a role of paralinguistic means in the masking process. People living in the northern parts of Europe greet each other with a very short handshake when shaking hands. For the nations of Southern Europe, Central and South America [6.P.105], it is customary to shake hands for a long time. In addition, it is also possible to hold the hand or wrist of the interlocutor with the left hand during hand greeting. In the countries of the African continent, they are often seen gently bending forward at the tips of their hands.

As the process of change of linguistic units in a language occurs over time, a similar change may occur in paralinguistic units - some of them may become obsolete and new tools may enter. For example, among the Uzbek and Tajik peoples, the custom of greeting by putting the hand on the chest is nowadays expressed more by shaking the head. It is known from the above that when learning another language, learning not only its vocabulary and grammatical structure, but also its paralinguistic tools will save it from being a foreigner when speaking with representatives of this language. Any language units on the higher level denotatively represent certain actions, things and events in objective existence.

That is, things, actions and events in objective existence (denotation) are reflected in the human mind (significant), and these concepts reflected in the mind are expressed with the help of a certain sound shell (word). Therefore, words reflect things, events and actions in objective existence, not directly, but through consciousness.

Also, gestures are characterized by a certain meaning in the mind. That is, the object and event (movement, state) of the objective existence is reflected in the mind and it is expressed through gestures. So, in this respect, both the word and the gesture perform the same function, both are signs. Gestures expressing a certain meaning in a specific speech situation are described using certain linguistic units in the process of retelling this speech situation. Therefore, every language has a number of verbs that represent gestures. These verbs are semantically referred to as indicative verbs. For example, he winked, turned his lips, etc. Human facial expressions and hand movements have a natural and conditional character. For example, a lip movement or a hand movement to drive away a fly that lands on the lip is a natural movement. Because these actions do not provide any information for the listener. A flick of the lower lip to the right (sometimes to the left) while looking at the listener means that he needs to get out of here. So, it gives certain information. Therefore, this action has a conditional character.

As can be seen from the above-mentioned points, the linguocultural approach is important during the study of paralinguistic tools. When people know a certain language completely, if they do not have information about the national culture, customs, and national conditions of the speakers of this language, they will have difficulties in understanding each other. Therefore, the comparative study of the non-verbal means of the peoples of the world greatly contributes to the development of cultural relations between the peoples and is of great importance in linguistics.

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